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Kick Off Meeting | ERC-CoG-2023 REDMIX

Unpacking Mixedness for an Inclusive History of the Red Sea, 1800s-2000s

UNLOCKING THE RED SEA'S MIXEDNESS

Turin, 25 - 26 March 2025
Archivio di Stato di Torino

The launch event of the REDMIX project will feature a keynote lecture and thematic sessions. The event will explore the historical dynamics of the Red Sea, the role of mixed ancestry people in its socio-political transformations, and the methodological innovations that guide REDMIX.

By bringing together experts from different disciplines, the launch will lay the groundwork for a pioneering exploration of the history of mixedness in the region and its wider implications.

Scientific Committee:

Francesco Dragone, Valentina Fusari,
Pierangelo Gentile, Lawrence Hirschfeld,
Sara Zanotta

Geographia Blaviana. Quorum IX. Hispaniam, Africam; Biblioteca Antica, Y 9 III

Archivio di Stato di Torino
Sezione Corte | Auditorium
Piazzetta Mollino, Torino

UNIVERSITÀ
DI TORINO

SSST
SCUOLA DI STUDI SUPERIORI
FERDINANDO ROSSI
UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI DI TORINO

ASSI
ALLEANZA SCUOLE
SUPERIORI D'ATENEO

UNLOCKING THE RED SEA'S MIXEDNESS

25 MARCH 2025

10:00 - 10:30 Welcome Message

Alessandra Panzanelli, Deputy Head, Internationalization, Historical Studies - University of Turin
Vincenzo Crupi, President of the SSST 'Ferdinando Rossi' School of Honor - University of Turin

10:30 - 12:30 Keynote Lecture | Chair Valentina Fusari

Ann Laura Stoler - The New School for Social Research
The Bend of Archival Light: On the Politics of Documentality

12:30 - 14:00 | Light Lunch

14:00 - 16:30 Red Sea Trajectories | Chair Sara Zanotta

Jonathan Miran - Western Washington University
Uncovering Marginalized Voices in the Red Sea:
Testimonies of Enslaved Maritime Runaways, 1900s-1910s

Anne Katrine Bang - University of Bergen
The Sudan Red Sea and the SNAC Project at CMI/UiB:
Digital Heritage Preservation Partnerships and Concerns in a Wider Context

Massimo Zaccaria - University of Pavia

The Place of Military History in the Red Sea Studies: Some Insights from the Italian Colonial Period

26 MARCH 2025

9:00 - 10:00 Visit to the Archivio di Stato di Torino - Sezione Corte

Luisa Gentile - State Archives of Turin

10:00 - 10:30 | Coffee Break

10:30 - 13:00 Traces of Mixedness | Chair Adnen el Ghali

Lina Fruzzetti - Brown University
Visualizing Our History: The Journeys, Lives and Identities that Marked Us

Samson Abebe Bezabeh - Hong Kong University
Beyond Ethno/Nationalist Historiographies:
Arabs and Other Mixed Families in the Making of Ethiopia

Marina de Regt - Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam
Muwalladeen in Yemen: Stigmatization, Discrimination and Radicalization in Times of War

13:00 - 14:30 | Light Lunch

14:30 - 16:30 | Meet the REDMIX Team

Valentina Fusari, Sara Zanotta, Adnen el Ghali, Tiziana Pasciuto, Francesco Dragone
University of Turin

16:30 - 17:00 | Coffee Break

17:00 - 18:00 | Wrap Up

Archivio di Stato di Torino
Sezione Corte | Auditorium
Piazzetta Mollino - Torino

REGISTER NOW

Administrative Office: Sara Amerio
Info: redmix@unito.it
dipstudistorici.unito.it

In My Mother's House

di Lina Fruzzetti e Ákos Östör
(2016, 82 min, Italia, USA, Eritrea VO con sottotitoli in inglese)

Intervengono

Lina Fruzzetti, Brown University

Ákos Östör, Wesleyan University

Francesco Dragone, Università di Torino

Daniela Ricci, Archivio Nazionale Cinematografico della Resistenza

Micaela Veronesi, Archivio Nazionale Cinematografico della Resistenza

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FINO A ESAURIMENTO POSTI**

Cinema Centrale
Via Carlo Alberto, 27 Torino

25 Marzo 2025
Ore 18.30 - 20.30

redmix@unito.it